

LEARNING TECHNOLOGY ACCELERATOR LEA

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CURRENT STATE-OF-ART REPORT 2018 AND BEYOND

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1. INTRODUCTION

This is the LEA state-of-the-art (SotA) Learning technologies report which introduces the stage of innovation in learning technologies in 2018. This state-of-the-art analysis is the baseline for LEA project's PPI and PCP proposal preparation. In the Open Market Consultation these issues will be revisited and updated. LEA. This report will look into the state of learning technologies in the market based on the IMAILE extensive D2.1 Need and market analysis with identified Gap, which was conducted in July 2015. This report focuses on what has happened in Learning technologies over the last three years.

The purpose of this document is to:

1. Benchmark IMAILE Personalised Learning Environments' (PLEs') innovation potential compared to actual market
2. Provide updated market analysis on learntech market 2018 and upcoming trends beyond PLEs

This report will be a common tool (cross deliverable between WP 2, 3 and 5) to use for dialogue and to create a common understanding of Learntech for all stakeholders and in particular to train procurers into understanding the potential assistance which the solutions in the market could provide for their schools, teachers & students. This report will be the base of LEA PPI open market consultation and IPR search of innovative solutions according to the demand identified in WP 3.

This state-of-the-art study was conducted by a case study approach on key personalized learning environment suppliers. Eight companies were interviewed and they were asked to demonstrate their innovative features. The future trends were mainly explored through a literature review method.

2. Key Definitions

2.1 Learning technologies

Learning Technology can be defined as the broad range of communication, information and related technologies that can be used to support learning, teaching and assessment (Association for Learning Technology, 2018). Learning technologies could be software or hardware. Trends of the learning technology field has moved in the last two decades a few times. First from learning object repositories to Massive Open Online Courses (Gasevik et al., 2014). Later the focus shifted to learning management systems and then to personalized learning environments.

2.2 Personalised learning environments

Personalizing learning is the process which empowers the learner to decide what, where, when and how to learn (Campbell & al., 2007), and to promote personal development through self-realization, self-enhancement, self-regulation and self-development. Personalized learning is about increasing student participation and providing direction in the development of twenty-first century education. (Jasute & al., 2016)

The rationale for personalized learning is to meet the needs, goals and preferences of the learner in order to ensure that every student achieves the highest possible standard. In relation to the personalization of education, the focus is on lifelong learning; people do not learn for the school, but for life (OECD, 2006).

Mark van Harmelen (2006) defines Personal Learning Environments' as systems that help learners take control of and manage their own learning. This includes providing support for learners to set their own learning goals, manage their learning; managing both content and process, communicate with others in the process of learning, and thereby achieve learning goals. A PLE may be composed

of one or more sub-systems: As such it may be a desktop application, or composed of one or more web-based services.

In the learning personalization process, support is provided to individuals in identifying their needs. In learning personalization, the target is to know students well enough to make every learning experience motivating, so that the students would learn more and lifelong (Wanner & Palmer, 2015).

During the IMAILE ¹project, the challenge of increased need for personalized learning was identified as the main need in European schools participating. Within IMALE pre-commercial procurement process, PLE suppliers developing their systems forwards were particularly advancing innovative technologies around learning analytics, artificial intelligence and intelligent tutoring systems as well as gamification elements. At the end of 2017, the clear trends in PLEs included the following functionalities (See table 1):

IMAILE Personalised learning trends 2017
Learning analytics
Artificial intelligence
Intelligent tutoring, content recommendations
Gamification (Badges, Leader boards)
Social tools for teachers, students, parents
Analytics dashboard
Interoperable content creation tools LT Standards (xAPI, HP5 tools etc.)
Content sharing & access to ready-made content (Libraries, ePortfolio tools, Teacher's incentive to get involved

¹ www.imaile.eu

Table 1: IMAILE Personalised learning environments innovative features list

This LEA State-of-the-art analysis continues the work of IMAILE in the area of personalized learning environments.

3. METHODOLOGY

LEA State-of-the-art analysis followed the case study methodology. The main research questions included:

1. What is innovative/trendy in current personalized learning?
2. What are the future trends in learning technologies overall?

The first question was tackled from the basis of the IMAILE deliverable D2.1. Need and Market analysis with identified innovation gap, which was published in July 2015, so three years ago. IMAILE D6.6 Final Testing report was also exploited to discover the level of innovation within the chosen IMAILE STEM PLEs. Case study approach (Yin, 2011) was then conducted to benchmark the IMAILE solutions innovation towards the market leaders. Based on challenges & features identified in IMAILE project, current PLE solutions in the market were analysed. The following methodology was utilized:

1. Identification of PLE solutions in the market setting to IMAILE criteria (n=43)
2. Interviews with KEY suppliers (n= 8) sampling strategy was based upon confirming or disconfirming cases (Kuzel, 1992) which was meaningful as IMAILE solutions already provided a starting point. The interview grid can be found from the annex 1 of this document.
3. Demo accounts and show cases were analysed to verify the suppliers' claims
4. The results were analysed and are described in chapter 4 of this document with the summary in chapter 5: What is state-of-the-art PLE like? Where are the innovation gaps?

Key suppliers (Table 2) were selected to the case study sample based on the maximum variation (Kuzel, 1992) sampling method. The idea was to generate a representative sample (Cao et al., 2002) of current personalized learning environments in the market based on their years of operation (start-ups to

established companies), but also selecting the sample based on the criteria rising from the IMAILE project's list of innovative features (see chapter 2.2. table 1 for the list). Second criteria was that these companies need to be operating in at least one of the LEA procuring markets (Sweden, Finland, Germany, Spain, Portugal, Italy). With this qualitative methodology, representative situation of the European personalized learning environments state-of-the-art can be determined for 2018.

Key suppliers table	Website	Screncap of interface
Blackboard	https://www.blackboard.com/	
Microsoft Delve	https://microsoft.com	
Claned	https://claned.com/	
It's Learning	itslearning.com/	

Mobie Academy	www.mobieacademy.fi	
Priima	www.disendum.com	
Peda.net	https://peda.net/	
Qridi	http://www.qridi.com/	

Table 2: Key stakeholders interviewed for the LEA State-of-the-art PLEs Case study

Show case was requested as industry sellers often claim many technologies which then in the real classroom settings either 1) Do not exist, 2) Are really difficult to use or 3) Are not really delivering the promised functionalities. So in the convenience of the LEA State-of-the-art time schedule, the market was asked to demonstrate their innovative features in action, with a populated system (as the nature of learning

analytics/AI cannot be shown without a prolonged period of use from both teacher & student side). Demo accounts were also asked and received from most suppliers, however, in many cases they cannot demonstrate those functionalities which require interaction from other users also. Evaluating PLEs is a complicated procedure which can only be properly conducted over a longer period (e.g. weeks, preferably months).

Figure 1: Some examples of the requested showcases in the LEA SoTA analysis

4. CURRENT TRENDS IN PERSONALISED LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS

IMAILE PLE:s were developed using Learning Analytics to support the students and teachers. Some preliminary Artificial Intelligence functionalities were tested using a Virtual tutor. In LEA we will proceed to investigate Artificial Intelligence for learning in depth followed by a common definition. (See figure 2 and 3)

IMAILE STEM PLEs introduced the following innovative features: (See D6.6. Testing Report for further description of the features www.imaile.eu)

- Analytics Dashboard
- Intelligent Tutoring System & Alerts
- Gamification by badges
- Lifelong learning ePortfolio
- Portability Authoring tool
- History Creation tool
- Virtual Tutor
- Personalised learning paths
- Progress tool
- Quick assessment tool
- Notification centre
- Gamification
- User interface for K-12 students
- STEM Career recommender

4.1 Learning Technology Standards

Understanding learning standards and standardization processes has become important because new technologies, new methods of working, businesses and new organizations are emerging. All actors' in the standardization process should more thoroughly understand their role in the process, and recognize the important

relations in the ecosystem. To ensure the applicability of technology enhanced learning solutions, it is therefore critical to understand and comply with a critical amount of relevant standards. Interoperability is a key issue when designing systems. It used to be that if you designed a system that 'locked all the doors' and was not compatible with any related systems, you could control the entire market. Luckily the current technology providers think different: Data is only useful if someone is using it. And more compatible and interoperable your system is with others in the field, more likely it is that your system will be used.

The 21st century education is also turning mobile based, implementing new pedagogical methods and techniques. The common factor for this paradigm change are new standards. The de-facto "programming language" for Internet is HTML5 and new standard for learning content is xApi. (See table 1)

In the field of learning technologies, there is a wide range of standards for various purposes such as:

- Architecture
- Metadata
- Content packaging
- Content discovery
- Learning Technologies Interoperability
- Quality
- Accessibility
- Portfolios
- Harvesting
- Information
- Legislation
- Interfaces
- Services Etc.

Table 2: Imaile suppliers standards choice(s)

	IMAILE suppliers choice(s)
Metadata	IEEE LOM
Content packaging	SCORM was a requirement
LA interoperability	xAPI
Tool integration	H5P
Learning Tools Interoperability	IMS LTI
Quiz Tool Interoperability	QTI
Quality	None chosen
Accessibility	W3C Web Accessibility (WAI) (partially)
Portfolios	No common approach
Harvesting	Harvesting was not explored
Content discovery	Not explored by IMAILE suppliers
Architecture	Not explored by IMAILE suppliers
Legislation	XÖV & Saga (partially)
Interfaces	No common approach
Services	IMS LIP / LIS / LTI
Identification	Oauth
XML + Web services	SOAP, REST

LEA case studies showed that most suppliers currently focus on xAPI and H5P tools, but some are still compatible with old standards like SCORM. However, the LEA interviewed suppliers did not see a future for SCORM packages. It is more and more important to be able to gather learning data from external tools (e.g. via XAPI and LTI interface) because learning is happening not only in the personalized learning platforms but for example in games or other informal means of learning.

4.2 Content Creation Tools

The current trend in Personalised Learning Environments is to support the interaction between students and teachers with social tools such as chat or discussion functionalities. The 21st century skills are more in the focus and the ICT working skills

ought to be taught in schools in a similar manner to reading and writing. This demands the PLEs to have more tools for content creation both for teachers and students.

The basic text editors which one can add e.g. photos, videos and audios is state-of-the-art. H5P like xApi based tools are needed to create interactive content and new forms of assessments but also for students to have more possibilities to show their competences and skills.

LEA Case Studies showed that many PLEs provide basic content creation tools for both teachers and students, but only a few of them provide 'emerging content creation tools' such as

- Pokemon Go-like map based content creation tools (1/8 providers) (See figure 2)
- Virtual/Augmented/Mixed reality content creation (none)
- Avatar based content creation(none or the interviewed, but some exist in the market)

Figure 2: Pokemon go style augmented reality content, (Picture source: <https://static.independent.co.uk/s3fs-public/thumbnails/image/2016/07/18/10/pokemon-go-walking.jpg>)

4.5 Learning Analytics

Learning analytics that measure data such as user or social data can provide a basis of different learning support systems (Elias, 2012; Ferguson 2012; Massart & Shulman, 2013; Shane, 2011). To understand what is meant by learning analytics – the user must understand that basically the system itself measures data and then produces some 'interactions or help' to the user himself or to the teacher/parent/headmaster or the relevant stakeholder group based. However, the current learning analytics solutions do not support the pedagogy up to their full potential (Sjöden, 2017).

So theoretically the important questions around learning analytics are:

1. What data is measured?
2. How is it used to provide support to the relevant user?

The LEA State-of-the-art analysis showed that the current solutions in the market typically measure user or social data, but not really learning data. If learning data is measured, it is based on quizzes where teacher has to regulate 'what is learning', which makes it time consuming and is rather non-automatic. (See figure 3)

Figure 3: Daily Genius learning analytics levels (Source: <https://i.pinimg.com/originals/4b/4b/4a/4b4b4a2b54a3db9d2171fad175105b9e.jpg>)

Current solutions in the market also do not provide much support to the teacher/student. In the level description of figure 4, it could be said that most PLEs in the market provide only level 1 type of information to the users, not explaining why this result has happened and certainly not even the prediction of what will happen if the student keeps on working the same way as before – nor do they provide actual guidance of what should be done to correct this situation. Many of them use learning analytics to give content recommendations, but not really recommendations on peer support or clues of how to complete the difficult tasks. It is typical that learning analytics results are presented to the users in a dashboard format, but the graphs are not always intuitively described.

Figure 4: Blackboard blog presentation of Learning analytics (Picture source: <https://blog.blackboard.com/wp-content/uploads/xray-blog-graphic.png>)

4.7 Personalized Learning Paths

Learning analytics could also be used to provide guidance to the user towards his/her tailored 'learning path'. For example if the system detects that the tasks that the student is working on are 'too easy', higher level tasks could be recommended. This is possible to achieve with current technologies, but usually the current state-of-the-art PLEs do not really automatically adapt. This means that teachers can design content for example on three levels (easy, medium, hard) and the system adapts to the level of the student. However, the current 'adaptive' systems still require a lot of work from teachers and are time-consuming. In the future, the learning paths could be adapted through AI and machine learning techniques which would learn of the learner's needs and adapt to their pace, learning preferences etc.

4.8 Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Three general types of AI can be distinguished (Walsh, 2018):

Weak AI: Found in machines and/or systems that equals or exceeds the human capabilities at a particular task requiring intelligence. This means that at the core of

AI are algorithms and data. This can be found in "on the market solutions" today also known as Assisted Intelligence.

Artificial General Intelligence (AGI): Machines/systems with the ability to work on any problem that humans can do at or above the level of humans.

This correlates to **Augmented Intelligence**, where humans and machines learn from each other and redefine the breadth and depth of what they do together, and/or to Autonomous intelligence, where adaptive/continuous systems take over in some cases.

2018 has been named as the "Year of artificial intelligence", which means that as far as technology trends go, it is considered cutting edge. Artificial intelligence can be defined as simulating human intelligence processes in machines, such as computer's information systems (Russel & Norvig, 2016).

The major step from learning analytics to "Artificial intelligence" has not yet been taken by most of the state-of-the-art PLE:s in the market showed the LEA state-of-the-art analystis. If the PLE:s would reach a so-called "Machine learning or Deep learning level", where the system itself starts to learn from the data that it is processing it could be possible to overcome issues like smart personalized recommendations to students and teachers, identifying potential drop-out students early and to analyze the student's life long learning beyond one task or course. The current systems on the market have not yet demonstrated that they have enough learning data to show artificial intelligence benefits. Machine learning requires constant use of the PLE in order to gather enough data to start the intelligent processes. The teachers might be using PLE:s irregularly and not in their every day teaching, which means that there is not enough data to show the results of such advances of technology. This is one of the reasons why currently those European PLE:s in the market that claim that they have 'AI' algorithms, do not have evidence to support their claims.

4.9 Gamification

Gamification is an element which can be understood in various ways in the context of personalized learning environments. The industry has often defined gamification as “the process of using game thinking and game mechanics to solve problems and engage users” (Zicherman, 2011). In the LEA state-of-the-art analysis, it was clear that many PLE providers see badges, leader boards or games within the PLEs as ‘gamification’ (see Figure 5). Gamification has been a trendy topic in the last 10 years, but currently it is seen as a contradictory issue as some teachers & schools do not think that for example leader boards or competition show the right kind of motivation for some of the students. Some PLE providers have even stated that they do not aim to provide any gamification due to this aspect.

Figure 5: Open Badges (Picture source: <https://i.ytimg.com/vi/2PKS2GajgME/maxresdefault.jpg>)

4.10 Virtual Tutor

Virtual tutors (See figure 6) are personal assistants which could provide support to the teacher/learner, however the LEA state-of-the-art analysis showed that there are very little virtual tutors in the market. Some claim that the virtual tutors speak in

the voice of the “artificial intelligence”, but no evidence of machine learning was shown in the case studies which LEA conducted. (See figure 10)

Figure 6: Example of a virtual tutor (Yiptree System, source: <https://yiptree.com/>)

4.11 Data Security

In May 25th 2018, European commission issued the GDPR – General Data Protection Regulation. GDPR is a challenge for organisations in every sector. But it's particularly tough for schools, as you have limited resources yet handle a high volume of sensitive data relating to both students and staff. Essentially, it's an EU regulation that's designed to strengthen data protection for everyone in the public, private and third sector, giving back control to individuals. GDPR covers data stored on servers, databases, websites and even on paper. And it's being introduced because of the huge advances in technology, which have had an incredible impact on the way data is used and stored.

Whenever an electronic service is required to process personal data, including pseudonymized personal data, the personal data protection legislation must be taken into account. In principle, the use of ICTs in educational institutions is permitted when it comes to the use of electronic tools for teaching. However, a mere attempt to facilitate digitalisation or the task of a controller does not justify the processing of personal data. When introducing electronic services, it is first necessary to evaluate whether the service performs something to the educational institution as required by the law. Even if the controller uses an external service

provider to produce electronic services, personal data will continue to be processed.

Personal data for pupils and students can only be processed for the purpose of teaching or training. The personal data handler can not use the contract to implement its own external affairs, such as for commercial purposes, and may not process personal data contrary to the controller's instructions.

(GDPR, Article 29)

According to the Data Protection Regulation, the Personal Data Handler may not use the services of another Personal Data Processor without the prior written or special prior written permission of the controller. Where a prior authorization has been given in writing, the personal data handler must inform the controller of any proposed changes to the addition or replacement of other personal data handlers and thus allow the controller to oppose such changes. Article 28 of the Data Protection Regulation. In other words, the service provider can not outsource the processing of personal data to another service provider without knowing the controller.

In order to comply with the principle of minimizing the information on the processing of personal data, the institutions may only deal with personal data necessary for the provision of teaching. The principle also extends to the use of electronic services. While digital services provide more extensive and more flexible resources for teaching, the electronic environment of students, students and their activities will easily accumulate more information than before. If the objectives for the organization of teaching were previously achieved in other ways, the registrar should be prepared to justify why the intended outcome could not have been achieved by the processing of personal data, or perhaps even completely, without it.

If a student or student exercises the right to request personal data removal or rectification or limitation of processing, the controller shall inform all such personal data about the persons to whom the personal data have been disclosed. In

addition, the registrar must inform the student or student of such recipients if he so requests. Article 19 of the Data Protection Regulation."

LEA State-of-the-art analysis showed that overseas companies like Blackboard specifically from United States of America are limiting their products from the European market thanks to GDPR, as the data regulations in United States of America are more loose. Specifically the use of AI / Learning analytics becomes rather difficult for the companies, as they cannot gather, store and organize personal data and therefore during the LEA state-of-the-art analysis interviews, the Blackboard representative explained that they are only offering solutions with AI to the American market and not to Europe. However on the other hand, European companies seem to be complying with GDPR as the sanctions can be so heavy. This might mean that data protection becomes a valuable marketing point for European companies' products.

5. SUMMARY OF CURRENT PLE TECHNOLOGY SOLUTIONS

To simplify the LEA State-of-the-art research results, figure 7 was drawn to illustrate the situation. It is clear that even in the last 3 years when IMAILE was on-going and doing research and development in PLEs, also the market solutions were progressing. Some innovative features have become standards in the field and some PLE providers have taken a 'conservative approach' only following the innovation after it happens, rather than becoming the front seat drivers in learning technologies. The analysis clearly shows that there is an innovation gap regarding artificial intelligence, as no solution in the market has been able to demonstrate the algorithms in action. Virtual tutors have not yet penetrated the market either, where as social media tools and mobile interfaces start to be 'old school technology' at this point.

SotA PLEs 2018	it's Learning	Blackboard	Canvas LMS	CLANED	DISCENDUM	QRiDi	ONEDU
Analytics dashboard	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Personalised learning paths	✓	?		✓			✓
Gamification	✓			✓	Open Badges		✓
Virtual tutor							Planned
Open standards like xAPI, HP5	✓			✓			✓
Social media	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Learning Analytics	User Data	Only in US	User Data	✓		Self assess	User Data
AI				✓?			Under development
GDPR		✗		✓			✓

Figure 7: Summary of the LEA State-of-the-art case study results

6 Future technology trends

“Prediction is very difficult, especially if it's about the future.” -Niels Bohr

The future technology trends section is written based on literature review as well as weak-signals rising in the LT experts interviewed in the case study. One of the questions in the grid was to envision the future of learning technologies and what types of trends do the suppliers see.

Children starting their school this year will be working till 2070 (See figure 8)(Frey & Osborne, 2013). A lot will change in that time and the technology will undoubtedly overtake some jobs that are familiar today. The children have to adjust to the changing environment for their whole life and they have to be life long learners. In this analysis we are taking a look at some of the trends affecting teaching and learning in the next decade. The paradigm shift has five

stakeholders, the learner, the teacher, the school, the parents and the developers.

FIGURE III. The distribution of BLS 2010 occupational employment over the probability of computerisation, along with the share in low, medium and high probability categories. Note that the total area under all curves is equal to total US employment.

Figure 8: AI affects on the labour market (Frey & Osborne, 2013)

The learning has changed in the free time of the children already. By watching gameplay videos, children may know how to play a game they never tried before. Bicycles and electronic devices can be repaired with the help of video tutorials and no expertise is needed to carry out multiphase problems. (See figure 9)

How to prepare our Youth for jobs that don't exist yet?

Figure 9: A THREE STAGE PLAN TO PREPARE OUR YOUTH FOR JOBS THAT DON'T EXIST (Neelen & Kirchner, 2017)

The teachers have to adapt to this new situation. Lecturing isn't necessarily the most effective way to teach, but the teachers need to have time to try out the new technologies and make material for them to try them out. The schools have to be the ones helping teachers, providing them with new technology and giving the teachers time to tinker with the new technology. The parents need education about the new classroom and the new ways students are learning. The developers need a hands on feel of the classroom. New technology itself isn't helping anyone by itself, there needs to be a use and a need for it.

This analysis reviews the current technology and extrapolates on it to find out where the next paradigm shifts might lay in.

6.1 Diverse and Specific Technologies

The technologies making most waves at the moment (e.g. AI) can be used indirectly to help students, help the teacher teach or grade, or help the learner understand the subject better.

It can be stated with almost definite certainty, that future technologies helpful to teachers and students will have something to do with AI, at least at an indirect

level. In future visions, computers alert the teacher or suggest certain type of material for the learner, if the student is making certain kinds of mistakes. AI could also play a role in suggesting training for teachers that cannot mediate certain subjects to their students.

Technologies that could make teaching easier are abundant, but at this time, they are also lacking implementations. Virtual reality (VR) could help history teachers take their students to any time to make their own observations, or geography teachers could take students anywhere in the world. The material would be hard and costly to make, and teachers themselves probably could not do it themselves. However, Pokemon Go -style content could be feasible and easy enough to implement.

Technologies making learning easier are here already. Duolingo gamifies and funnifies language learning and different kinds of wearable technologies such as FitBit-gear can gamify physical exercise. Hopefully we will see open source platforms for other gamification and funnification programs that the teachers could modify for their own purposes.

6.2 Practical Applications of Technological Innovation

There's a lot of hype surrounding several new technologies, such as augmented reality (AR), wearable technology or artificial intelligence implementations. New technologies are being developed and they are predicted to play a role in education, but only a few future technologies have been identified to have implementations as an actual learning technology at this time. Google Glasses was discussed a lot in 2012, but people preferred their handheld devices compared to an eyeglass-type interface. The preference of certain types of technology is one thing, the other would be the robustness and flexibility of the technology. New technology always has a price tag, which consists of both monetary value and the time spent getting familiar with it and making material for it. The teachers have a certain plot line for their classes and courses, into which the

new technology has to fit. Either the old pedagogical solutions are presented in a new way or there is a new angle for the whole subject. Many technological advances are left to the 'shelf' as there is no pedagogy behind the design or no training for the teachers.

In addition to the technology, teachers need curricula-fitting learning materials working on the solution - either they get the material ready or they make it themselves. If the technology is cheap and easy to use, it can be acquired for just a few presentations. For example, the blue-red 3D-glasses are inexpensive and they could be bought for mathematics class just to show a few 3D plots during a semester. More expensive equipment has to be robust and have more implementations. True VR- or AR-technology can be used in simulation learning for firemen and ambulance units. In those implementations, the technology gives reproducible environment to train with and would probably cut costs swiftly. The technologies themselves cannot teach and thus, the teachers have to find the cognitive benefits. Then again, the teachers might not be able to find the benefits, if they do not have the possibility to tinker with the new technology. There is an old saying that the teachers teach the way they have learned. How will the way teaching is performed change, if the teaching culture stays the same? The problem is to change the paradigm of teaching and learning, which might not be as rapid as one would hope it to be. In the worst case, the change will come with the new generation, once the older generation starts to retire. If we want to see faster results, the teachers willing to tinker and experiment with new technology should be supported with suitable material and training.

When asked what kind of technologies the teachers would need, the Northern European teachers usually talk about saving time; in the south – the lack of devices/student is a great problem (see further examples in LEA deliverables D3.2-D3.4. Regarding the needs analysis). The grading of STEM subjects can be automated up to a certain point, but the grading cannot consist of multiple choice questions. The situation for language teachers and humanistic discipline teachers is even worse, as essay type answers cannot be reliably graded

automatically. That is, not at least without artificial intelligence solutions, that could “understand” what the students are meaning with their language.

6.3 Artificial Intelligence (AI) of the future

As discussed previously, our state-of-the-art analysis showed that no solution in the market can actually demonstrate AI algorithms in action with a populated system. Some claim that they do work, but when asked to show case, cannot perform. Many suppliers did not even want to claim they have ‘AI’ but rather state that they have learning analytics at work instead.

Some reasons behind these findings could be that currently, there is not enough user data to enable support for teachers and learners. AI’s little brother, learning analytics, can be used, but it can only find correlations and anomalies in the student data. It can be used as an aid for the teachers as well as to find certain types of misunderstandings or gaps in knowledge.

Current solutions in the market mainly gather user data to be processed for the AI algorithms. User data consists of data from a certain user, which will accumulate as the user is using the service. Any AI that could deduce something from a sample this small, would have to be taught with massive database of earlier users. The GDPR could disallow this kind of data use.

However, the solutions in the market could be thought to measure “learning data” which consists of data that is based on learning evidence. The pedagogy behind algorithms has been rarely shown, but this is definitely a growing aspect in the market. Current solutions claim to measure learning data where learning is defined by the teacher – however, this could be more automatisized in the future.

As the state-of-the-art analyse showed, no solution could actually demonstrate AI in action with a populated system. A system that would actually be learning itself would require a large pool of users to teach the AI. The first ones to really get the benefits from the AI will probably be MOOC-services (Massive Open Online

Course) such as Coursera or Udemy. They can have millions of learners learning with the same material and having the same automatized tests. They also have the data from the time spent with each video and replays of the videos, from which an AI could observe patterns in different learners. They will likely be the first ones to have parallel material from the same topic for different types of learners. In the future, it will be interesting to see how these services will be developed.

6.4 Challenges of innovative future learning technology

There are always problems when teachers are introduced to new technology or they are responsible for introducing new technology to students. The cost of the new technology is a likely topic to raise discussion, but probably not the most important problem. Teachers are a heterogeneous set of people and there are the technophiles that will buy the technology for themselves and learn to use it in their own time. There is also the conservative section that will not take any steps towards learning a new technology and will actively oppose the new methods. Between these two extremes, there is the majority that would use the new technology, but would need different levels of support and help. The students are even more heterogeneous, and implementing the technology to student use can be challenging. A biology teacher might want to focus on teaching biology, not how to use the new technologies in the class. Thus, students would need specific classes for the new technologies so that the subject teacher can concentrate on their own area of expertise.

1. A little or no ready-made curricula-fitting learning content for the new software/hardware/gadget
2. Design has not taken into account the pedagogical approach
3. Teachers do not get enough hands-on training or they have no time to learn how to use these technologies (Chew et al., 2018)
4. One solution may not fit all: Education landscape is diverse within Europe, within the countries and even within the same schools depending on teachers' age, topics to teach, devices available etc.
5. Teachers do not fully understand the benefits of using technology in their teaching.

7. CONCLUSIONS

LEA State-of-the-art analysis showed that innovation gaps still remain in both personalized learning environments as well as learning technologies in general. (See figure 10)

SotA PLEs 2018	it's Learning	Blackboard	D2L	CLANED	edmentum	QRiDi	ONEdu
Analytics dashboard	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Personalised learning paths	✓	?		✓			✓
Gamification	✓			✓	Open Badges		✓
Virtual tutor							Planned
Innovation Gaps in the market							
Open standards like xAPI, HP5	✓			✓			✓
Social media	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Learning Analytics	User Data	Only in US	User Data	✓		Self assess	User Data
AI				✓?			Under development
GDPR		✗		✓			✓

Figure 10: Innovation gaps in the Personalised Learning Environment market 2018.

To summarise the current trends in PLEs 2018 include:

- 1 Analytics Dashboards** – based on user/social data, not learning data
- 2 Personalised learning paths** – content recommendations by teachers manually, which makes it really time-consuming for teachers, not automated
- 3 Gamification** – leader boards, badges – many feel contradicted as some students may not benefit from competition
- 4 Virtual tutors** – not really appear in the market yet, but some are in the plans

- 5 **Use of Learning analytics / AI** – only user/social data measuring, not really supporting the learner/teacher/parent – No solution has shown AI in 'Action' with real populated data.
- 6 **Mobile first** – All have at least a scalable HTML 5 version working, many also support apps for apple and android phones. However, this trend seems to have become more like the must have rather than an innovative feature

Innovation gaps remain specifically on the field of learning analytics and artificial intelligence. In the future, virtual reality/augmented reality/mixed reality solutions are penetrating the field of education and there are some promising examples shown already. However the market is quite far from virtual /augmented/mixed reality content creation tools being easy-to-use or customer affordable. Recommendations for the LEA procurers based on this state-of-the-art analysis regarding innovation technology procurement are the following:

LEA Recommendations for LT procurers:

- 1 **Look for sustainable technology solutions** – Evaluate the life-span of the technology: Is this going to be available on 2030? Current VR glasses for example seem to be still finding their form. Can this be utilized through the curricula? Is the technology interesting for all grades of the K-12?
- 2 Can **1 Device: 1 Student ratio** be achieved by this technology? If not, how can the learning around the device be organized? Be critical. So many technology solutions are gathering dust in the corner of the classroom or the basement of the school.
- 3 **Protect students** – Pay attention to where the data is stored and how it is handled
- 4 **Demand ease of use & seamless experience** – Current LT systems are too complicated. If iPhone Apps take 15 minutes to learn how to use, this is how the LT market solutions should also work. New systems should also integrate with previous ones to bring sustainability and ease of use for the buyers.
- 5 **Testing in real classrooms with real students and teachers is crucial** – Purchasing based on the sales pitches alone are not recommendable. Comparing feature listings also do not give the real idea of how the technology works. LEA

recommendation is to write testing budget for teachers in innovation procurement projects so that they have enough time to give feedback and co-design the technologies in the process (e.g. one day a week with no teaching)

Biggest Learning technology advances for the future seem to be going to the direction:

1. Advances in **virtual reality** toward augmented and mixed reality – hologram meetings, hologram teaching, hologram screens etc.
2. Increase in **robots** and teaching programming & computational thinking throughout the curricula
3. Advances in **artificial intelligence** will enable adaptive learning content and automatic personalized learning support
4. Informal learning is going to start competing with formal learning – already the students are learning more and more through Youtube channels and their peer networks. **Blockchains** will also bring competition and reliability which might enable mixing of formal and informal learning in a way that is difficult to imagine in the current world.

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Annex 1: LEA State-of-the-art interview grid

Describe innovation in your company's personalized learning environment

What is new? What is trendy in PLEs?

What do you see in the future of PLEs?

Topics	Details		Evidence
Learning analytics	Measured data (user data, learning data)	Recommendations, assistance to teachers/students	Pictures/Video/Show case/Demo account/Populated account
Artificial intelligence	What is AI? (in comparison to Learning analytics)		Pictures/Video/Show case/Demo account/Populated account
Virtual tutors	Chat box	AI behind?	Pictures/Video/Show case/Demo account/Populated account
Gamification	Badges, Leader boards	What does it mean in your company's platform	Pictures/Video/Show case/Demo account/Populated account
Analytics dashboard	For teacher	For student, for parent	Pictures/Video/Show case/Demo account/Populated account
LT Standards	Interoperability, content creation	Security, GDPR	Pictures/Video/Show case/Demo account/Populated account
ePortfolio	Life long	Content creation	Pictures/Video/Show

	learning?	tools?	case/Demo account/Populated account
Future trends	Virtual reality, augmented reality, mixed reality	AI	Pictures/Video/Show case/Demo account/Populated account
Teacher's incentive to get involved	Time?	Money?	Pictures/Video/Show case/Demo account/Populated account

